

Characteristics Of Formation Of Phonemic Hearing Of Children With Dysatria

Nadejda Sosedova

PhD, Associate Professor of Speech Therapy Department
Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Abstract: *The article describes the features of the formation of phonemic hearing of children with dysatria, the study of speech development and the analysis of speech development disorders.*

Keywords — phonemic hearing, articulation, distinction of sounds, attention, prosody.

INTRODUCTION.

Acquiring the correct pronunciation of sounds develops on the basis of the close connection of sensory and motor functions, which ensure the unity of the speech system. On the one hand, the correct acquisition of the sound side of speech determines the development of the phonemic and perceptive level of perception in many ways. On the other hand, during the development of speech, the auditory analyzer feels the influence of the speech movement analyzer: the child hears and perceives the sounds as they pronounce them, the child is better distinguished by hearing the sounds he pronounces correctly, or vice versa.

Also, in order for the child to correctly form the sound side of speech, not only the articulating apparatus should be ready for it, but he should be able to hear well and have the ability to differentiate between his own and others' speech.

In children with mild dysarthria, the disturbance of the formation of phonemic hearing is secondary in nature. Defects of this type appear in pathological speech kinesthesias, in injuries to the motor organs of the speech organs, secondary phonemic hearing in children with mild dysarthria, the level of expression of which depends on the level of expression of the dysarthria itself.

Children perform poorly in differentiating close sounds (on the basis of pictures), choosing pictures for given sounds, familiarizing them with joints. In children with mild dysarthria, due to pathologies in the articulatory apparatus (gynertonus, hypotonus, deviation, hypertinesis, hypersolivation, etc.), the motility of articulatory organs is disturbed, articulatory movements deteriorate.

This motor deficiency has a negative effect on the formation of phonemic hearing. This first-syllable disorder resists changing the mental operations that make up phonemic awareness during training. Due to this, phonemic skills, skills, and imaginations that perform phonemic analysis in the mental framework (qualification) are not formed. Also, the structure of the connection between the hearing and speech movement apparatus leads to insufficient mastering of the sound content of the word, which, in turn, is reflected in the process of learning to read and write. Impaired clarity of articulation

during speech, unintelligible speech of children with mild dysarthria does not allow the formation of clear auditory perception. Children often cannot control their pronunciation.

Disruption of kinesthetic control and auditory differentiation is considered to be the cause of permanent impairment of prosodic and phonemic aspects of speech.

Our research on the phonemic hearing status of children with mild dysarthria has shown that some children have difficulty distinguishing non-speech sounds from level I.

Inability to distinguish non-speech sounds indicates a state of auditory attention and is considered a condition for phonemic hearing. Anamnesis is an interesting observation. Dearly, children with problems distinguishing all non-speech sounds have adenoid tumors (level II) in the otolaryngologist report. Another important observation is that children are better able to pronounce sounds that are familiar to them in their everyday life than sounds that are not introduced to them for the first time.

Many children, when tested for rhythmic ability and repetition of rhythmic lines, have errors in both. Due to unstable auditory attention, some tasks were completed after 2 or even 3 attempts. In this case, motor breakdown is clearly visible. Some children cannot complete these tasks, they refuse to complete the tasks. Children with mild dysarthria and children with dysarthria represent non-homogeneous groups when the discrimination of similar sound complexes and similar words according to sound content is examined. Deficiency is observed in everyone, but it is expressed in different degrees. Many children independently correct tasks completed with mistakes. Often, children do not notice their mistakes. Children perform the tasks of distinguishing and separating close words according to their sound content with difficulty. Applause is required in such assignments. If the speech therapist mispronounces a word out of many words, the child claps. (checkers, checkers, checkers). All children have difficulties in distinguishing syllables and phonemes, only after several attempts (2-four times) children can distinguish a given vowel sound from a series of other vowels. Not all children are able to distinguish opposition consonant syllables: syllables with voiced and unvoiced sounds.

In the study of syllables and phonemes, it was found that 1/1 of the children had impaired speech-listening memory.

Challenges of agatnyi is observed not only in distinguishing sounds that differ according to subtle acoustic-articulatory signs, but also in specific sounds. In some children with mild dysarthria, the main difficulty is found in repeating the chain of joints. Specific disorders are reflected in the adaptation of the second link to the first, in the replacement of links in the chain of links. Many scientists suggest that the successful elimination of phonetic, lexical-grammatical disorders, the prevention of dysmorphography and dyslexia, the formation of phonemic hearing, in addition, good phonemic hearing helps children to distinguish prosodic characteristics in the speech of others and allows to successfully eliminate prosody deficiencies.

Correcting the pronunciation of sounds. The principle of individual approach is used to correct the pronunciation of sounds. Correcting sounds and putting them into speech is selected individually. Working on multiple sounds requires consistency in work. In the correction work, first of all, sounds that are easy to pronounce from an articulatory point of view or that are easy to correct are selected. These sounds; a, p, u, m, k, n, x, B, o, t, s, l. In the process of working on these sounds, they can be brought up to the standard of pronunciation. Along with working on the above-mentioned sounds, work is also carried out on the development of phonemic hearing and the formation of sound analysis skills.

In severe cases of articulatory disorders, putting sounds into speech requires special help. In this case, the speech therapist explains and helps the child to perform the movement necessary for the pronunciation of this or that sound, using vision, tactile-vibrational perception. For example, in anarthria, the speech therapist brings his hand closer to the child's lips to produce the articulation of the sound "u".

When working on punctuation of sounds, the speech therapist should approximate the sound to the correct level of pronunciation, even if it is not clear. In the beginning, it is difficult to achieve a normal pronunciation. At this time, it is very important for the child to distinguish similar sounds. The degree of approximation of sounds to the normal pronunciation is determined by the degree of damage to the articulatory apparatus. When working on each new sound, it is necessary to study its articulatory features, that is, the main characteristic signs of articulation, its difference from other sounds, to compare the articulation with others.

Regular exercises bring the sound closer to the desired articulatory order and move to a full sound pronunciation. The speech therapist gradually requires clear and different pronunciation of the studied sound.

In addition to working on articulatory motor skills and putting sounds into speech, regular work is done to develop phonemic hearing. In this way, children learn to separate and analyze the necessary vowel sounds from a series of vowels, and consonants from a series of consonants. Children learn to repeat the sounds they learn in different combinations of

syllables, to say the sounds that make up syllables and words, and to determine their sequence.

In the pronunciation classes, the works aimed at developing the members of the articulatory apparatus are carried out frontally. The exercises used are selected taking into account the speech situation of the individual development of children. In addition, breathing exercises are also carried out during training. The main part of the lessons is devoted to the pronunciation and strengthening of the learned sound separately and in combination of syllables. The speech therapist should always check how the child has mastered the lessons. For this, the child is asked to tell or show the position of the organs of articulation that is characteristic of this or that sound, and then is asked to pronounce the sound separately and in words. Exercises on sounds are controlled under visual and tactile perception

References

- [1] Abidova, N. (2022). Problems of Preparing Future Defectologists to Work in the Conditions of Inclusive Education. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 2505-2511.
- [2] Abidova, N. (2021). Organization Of The Work Of The Logo Teacher With Children With Disabilities In The Conditions Of Inclusive Preschool Practice. *Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation*, 33382-33398.
- [3] Abidova, N. Z. (2013). Peculiarities of the Formation and Development of Vocabulary in Children with Vision Disorders. *European Researcher*, (2-3), 475-479.
- [4] Nilufar Abidova. (2021). Inclusive Education Of Children With Special Educational Needs. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(03), 476-480. <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajssei/Volume03Issue03-74>
- [5] Akimenko, V. M. Developmental technologies in speech therapy uText / V. M. Akimenko. – Rostov n/a. : Phoenix, 2011. – 109 p.
- [6] Gvozdev, A. N. Questions of studying children's speech uText / A. N. Gvozdev. – St. Petersburg : Childhood-Press, 2007. – 472 p.
- [7] Gomzyak, O. S. Speak correctly at 6-7 years old yuText / O. S. Gomzyak. – M.: Gnom i D, 2009. – 160 p.
- [8] Filicheva, T. B. Uchebnoye posobiye dlya logopedov i vospitateley detskix sadov s narusheniyami rechi [Tekst] / T. B. Filicheva, G. V. Chirkina. – M. : MGOPi, 1993. –232 s.
- [9] Fomicheva, M.F. Education of children in correct sound pronunciation yuText: textbook. allowance / M. F. Fomicheva. – M.: Education, 1989. – 239 p.